

Accidents Happen - Anthrax Management in Australia and Global Trends

By Joanne Beilby

Author: Beilby, J. ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9345-8307>

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Abstract This archival research reviews non-bioterrorism anthrax outbreaks since the 1960s and compares Australian primary health care responses with practices in developing countries. It discusses transmission routes, clinical manifestations in humans and animals, diagnostics, vaccines, public health management, and the economic impacts on the meat industry. Originally published on 26 March 2011 on the Malaria Ramblings blog, this edition preserves the original content in a modernised, citable format.

INTRODUCTION

On the 4th of March, 2007, a community social event in Australia was inadvertently supplied with Anthrax infected beef carcasses by a local farmer, for use at a spit roast. Coupled with insufficient cooking and the heat resistant properties of the Anthrax spores, consumption of the beef resulted in Gastrointestinal Anthrax infection in several people. They presented to Newcastle Regional Hospital on the 8th of March, 2007 for treatment and the diagnosis was made by the Local Medical Officer and reported to the National Notifiable Diseases Surveillance System. Concurrently, the local veterinarian was called to sick beef cattle in the area and the same diagnosis and notification was made.

The purpose of this paper is to review non-bioterrorism based global incidences of Anthrax infection since the 1960s and compare Australian primary health care response to an outbreak of this highly infectious disease, with practices in developing countries. Particular reference will be made to the economic impacts of the disease with regard to the meat industry. The illustrative purposes of which are to demonstrate the high level of surveillance and comprehensive primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary health care required to achieve a desired level of preventative health care, and the difficulties this poses for a developing country.

What is Anthrax?

Bacillus anthracis is a bacterial soil dwelling organism. It is sporulating, making it highly resistant to environmental stresses such as heat, cold, pH, disinfection, irradiation and other adverse conditions. The survival of the spores is made possible by several thick and impermeable protein layers surrounding the bacterium. As a result, *B. anthracis* can lie dormant awaiting favourable conditions for tens of years.

Bacillus anthracis causes an aggressive infectious disease called Bacillus Anthracosis and known as Anthrax. Anthrax is characterized by rapid and high mortality. It generally occurs in herd animals such

as cows, sheep, goats, camels and antelopes. It can also infect humans via contact or from consumption of infected animals or animal products, and bioterrorism agents.

TRANSMISSION & VECTORS

Epidemiology: How is Anthrax transmitted?

The epidemiology of Anthrax in humans is both agricultural and industrial.[i] Initially, animals can ingest Anthrax spores when grazing contaminated ground. Anthrax is then shed by a dead or dying animal infected with the disease, providing a source of infection for other animals and humans. Anthrax spores are heat resistant making it possible to contract the disease via ingestion of insufficiently cooked contaminated meat or via contact with an open skin wound, eyes or mucosal surface. Anthrax spores can be inhaled into the respiratory tract of people handling infected animal hides, hair, wool or meat, however transmission in this manner in an agricultural setting is rare.[ii]

Anthrax & Food

All continents are disease-endemic for Anthrax in tropical and sub-temperate areas. Globally, there have been numerous cases of Anthrax infection via the meat supply during the last fifty years. In the 1960s in the Bekaa Valley, Lebanon, several cases were reported due to consumption of raw goat meat infected with Anthrax.[iii] In Zimbabwe in the 1980s, over 9000 patients were infected with gastrointestinal Anthrax.[iv] In the 1980s, Thailand reported 74 cases due to consumption of infected water buffalo, bull and cow meat,[v] and in the year 2000, in Minnesota, USA, locally supplied Anthrax contaminated beef was consumed resulting in infection.[vi] In 2006, the Dobritch region of Bulgaria reported one case of Anthrax due to unvaccinated sheep.[vii]

Incidences of gastro-intestinal Anthrax have occurred in Iran, India, Thailand, Gambia and Uganda. In 1979, in Ekaterinburg, Russia (then Sverdlovsk), a large epidemic of Anthrax resulted in 60 cases and forty-two deaths.[viii] In Peru, from 2001-2006, 30-50 cases of Anthrax occurred annually. In 2007, nine cases of human cutaneous Anthrax occurred in the northern Province of Lambayeque, including one death.[ix]

In most industrialized countries during an outbreak, livestock are vaccinated against Anthrax. This is rarely the case in the developing world. Practices of slaughtering and eating infected animals in some developing countries are considered preferential to wasting scarce resources, hence the increased prevalence of outbreaks in these countries.

An example of an incidence of intentional consumption of infected meat came from India in 1989. Infection in an animal is highly visible due to massive bacteremia and it is highly unlikely that the Indian villagers consumed the meat unaware of its infectious status. The outbreak resulted in thirty cases of human anthrax in Ramabhadrapuram village of Chittoor district in Andhra Pradesh. All of the infected

were very poor Harijans. Of the 30 people infected, 25% died. They were all women with gastrointestinal Anthrax.[x]

In Chiang Mai in 1966, an incidence of Anthrax infection resulted from unintentional consumption of undercooked, infected meat by people who were unaware of the disease state of the animal, and the danger of exposure to infectious material. In Indonesia, in 2007, 10 confirmed reports of Anthrax amid reports of up to 761 cases emerged as a result of villagers slaughtering and consuming infected buffalo. Anthrax outbreaks were also confirmed in Guinea-Bissau, India, Indonesia, Krygyzstan, Mongolia, Peru, Togo, the United States, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

The lack of PHC is easily inferred by the incidence and nature of Anthrax outbreaks in these countries. Basic education and empowerment could easily have avoided many of these incidents. Unlike Australia, the response of many developing countries to an Anthrax outbreak is severely limited by resource constraints. There is a critical lack of financing and political commitment to develop and implement comprehensive PHC policy, particularly in the areas of complementary education. Supportive programmes in veterinary skills and safe food handling and preparation need to be developed and health promotion advanced. Further to this, empowering and educating locals to act as surveillance for the disease, monitoring and evaluating the safe handling of infected carcasses, would develop the participatory entitlements of people to ensure PHC in their community. Simple and relatively inexpensive programmes such as these would reduce the requirement for costly emergency responses to Anthrax outbreaks and reduce loss of life.

ANTHRAX DISEASE MANIFESTATIONS IN HUMANS

Anthrax infection in humans can range from sub-clinical to fatal and it is thought that the disease manifestation is closely related to a dose of viable spores and the immune state of the host.[xi] Anthrax is an under-diagnosed disease of rural areas that is manifested in humans in four ways:

1. Pulmonary (or inhalation) Anthrax;
2. Gastrointestinal Anthrax;
3. Cutaneous Anthrax; and
4. Anthrax meningitis.

Cutaneous anthrax is generally well recognized however Gastrointestinal Anthrax and Pulmonary Anthrax are less so. Due to its wide presentation, the extent of Anthrax infection in human populations is considered to be under appreciated and under reported, and the inclusion of Anthrax in disease differentials must be emphasized. All four syndromes have differing presentations and require immediate notification to local public health authorities.

Pulmonary Anthrax

Pulmonary Anthrax results from the inhalation of Anthrax spores into the lungs and respiratory tract. The incubation period is from 1 to 7 days however periods of up to 60 days have been documented. Initial symptoms lasting from a few hours to several days include fever, cough, headache, chills, emesis, dyspnea, chest pain, abdominal pain and weakness.[xii]

The next stage of the illness may be preceded by apparent improvement but quickly lapses into the more diagnostic symptoms of pyrexia, diaphoresis, cyanosis, hypotension, lymphadenopathy, shock and finally death. The onset of second stage symptoms may precede death by only a few hours.

Time from onset of initial symptoms to death averages three days. Early diagnosis (see Fig. 2) and treatment may increase the likelihood of survival however current statistics indicate 95% mortality.[xiii]

Gastrointestinal Anthrax

Gastrointestinal Anthrax results from the ingestion of Anthrax spores, usually via the consumption of contaminated meat. Gastrointestinal Anthrax is further sub-categorized into Oropharyngeal Anthrax and Abdominal Anthrax. The presentation of Gastrointestinal Anthrax in Australia is rare and most PHC physicians will not be familiar with the primary presentation. The former indicates the intake of spores into the upper gastrointestinal tract and is characterized by oral or oesophageal ulcer, regional lymphadenopathy and eventually sepsis. Abdominal Gastrointestinal Anthrax is characterized by nausea, vomiting, bloody diarrhea, acute abdomen and sepsis. Abdominal Anthrax is due to the ingestion of Anthrax spores into the lower gastrointestinal tract.[xiv]

Both Oropharyngeal Anthrax and Abdominal Anthrax result in approx 50% mortality with a risk of secondary Pulmonary Anthrax and Anthrax meningitis.[xv]

Cutaneous Anthrax

Cutaneous Anthrax is the most common manifestation of the disease and results from Anthrax spore penetration of an open skin wound, (often located on the limbs or face). The initial symptom is a small, usually pruritic papule that transforms into an ulcer of less than two cm in diameter within two days. The ulcer progressively develops into a small vesicle and finally to a black painless eschar, surrounded by localized oedematous tissue.

Over the following one to two weeks, the eschar will desiccate and wither. Regional lymphadenopathy or lymphadenitis may also occur and secondary sepsis may develop. Cutaneous Anthrax has a mortality rate of approx 20% in the absence of therapy; however this drops to 1% given timely antibiotic treatment.[xvi]

Anthrax Meningitis

Anthrax Meningitis may result as a secondary complication of any of the aforementioned forms of Anthrax. Symptoms include headache and meningismus. Anthrax meningitis carries a near 100% mortality.[xvii]

MANAGEMENT OF AFFECTED PATIENTS

Considerations & Requirements

The progression of Anthrax is rapid with high mortality. Therefore treatment should not be withheld pending laboratory results. Empirical therapy should be started immediately as any delay in treatment may increase the risk of mortality significantly. Intensive medical support including hospitalization, airway management, haemodynamic support, and organ system support may be necessary. Palliative care may be required.[xviii]

First-Line Treatments

Environmental Anthrax is usually sensitive to penicillin however bioterrorism strains will likely be resistant. Therefore, recommended first-line therapy is ciprofloxacin with doxycycline a suitable alternative. Treatment regime should continue for sixty days and sensitivity testing used to identify potentially resistant strains.[xix] For a tabulated summary of clinical findings, treatment and prognosis for Anthrax infection see Table 2.

ANTHRAX DISEASE MANIFESTATION IN ANIMALS

Symptoms, Signs and Tests in Herd Animals

Anthrax runs its course quickly in animals and detection of infection prior to death can consequently be difficult. It is therefore advisable to rule out Anthrax as the cause of death before the carcass is handled by others. This is crucial if the animal has died suddenly without having been observed as ill and if the meat is usually destined for consumption.

Clinical signs and symptoms of Anthrax in Herd Animals[xx]:

- Fever
- Diarrhoea
- Muscle tremors
- Respiratory distress
- Abortion
- Decline in milk production
- Convulsions
- Bloody discharge
- Swelling in the neck and shoulder areas

Herd animals infected with Anthrax usually die within 48 to 72 hours. Signs of the infection will be visible to farmers, handlers and butchers. After death, many visible signs of infection persist, especially mass hemorrhaging from the orifices as a symptom of clotting failure due to toxin released by *Bacillus anthracis*.^[xxi] There may be rapid bloating and an absence of rigor mortis.^[xxii] Veterinarians confirm Anthrax infection via blood smear stained with New Methylene Blue and analysed at a diagnostic laboratory or in the field by a District Veterinary Officer.

TESTING & DIAGNOSIS

Anthrax Testing in Humans

Several tests can be used to confirm Anthrax and to quantify the amount and stage of bacterial infection present.^[xxiii]

- Tissue Histology
- Blood Cultures
- Cerebrospinal Fluid Micro and Culture
- Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)
- Nasal Swab
- Antibody Quantification
- Infectious Serology

Such tests are performed under strict conditions by microbiologists, molecular pathologists and hematologists at a diagnostic laboratory.^[xxiv]

PUBLIC HEALTH: PREVENTION & VACCINES

Prevention for Humans: Vaccines

Currently, there is no vaccine against Anthrax that is approved for use in Australia. An FDA approved vaccine may be imported under special circumstances for those exposed to Anthrax spores: laboratory workers, abattoir workers, animal handlers, or professional cleaners of contaminated sites.^[xxv]

The FDA approved vaccine contains an antigen from a non-pathogenic strain, (the Sterne strain).^[xxvi] A series of six injections are required over an 18 month period to confer immunity. Some short term side effects of the vaccine can include localized reactions, muscle soreness and headaches. Reported long term side effects are yet to be confirmed.

Farmer & Handler OH&S

As prevention is the most effective method of controlling Anthrax infection, avoidance of contaminated livestock, animal produce and under-cooked meat is top priority. Furthermore, compliance with public health measures needs to observe the following: compliance with managing authorities, compliance with drug/vaccine regimes, maintenance of quarantine, responsible handling of infected animals, complete avoidance of contaminated meat and meat products.

IMPLICATIONS FOR THE MEAT INDUSTRY

The ramifications of an Anthrax outbreak for the commercial meat industry are very serious. Compromise of reputation as a safe and reliable meat exporter will see negative demand shocks affect the market in both the domestic and export sectors. A ban on meat exports will impair trade relations for years to come and loss of commercial viability for farmers, suppliers and associated businesses will see many suffering hardship and a loss of revenue. At a macro-economic level, price slumps across the market will be reflected in GDP, unemployment statistics and the CPI will increase as affordability is reduced by the absence of domestic suppliers in the market.

A single contaminated export of animal product can cripple the whole market and lead to huge economic losses. Correct management is vital. As a notifiable disease, Anthrax can be effectively and efficiently tracked by epidemiological authorities via identification tagging, tests on stomach contents, soil tests and DNA techniques.

An Anthrax outbreak would have a devastating effect on the domestic and export red meat and livestock industries. This was evidenced in 1997 when a multi-state outbreak in Victoria and New South Wales resulted in Indonesian import bans on Australian meat during the period. Over 1,600 tonnes of meat sales and \$1.6 million in revenue was lost.

	EU	West Europe	East Europe	USA	East USA	West Canada	East Canada	West Japan	Taiwan	Korea South	Other Asia	Middle East	Other Dest	Total
<i>Beef & Veal</i>	8456	7	12537	196715	98552	6171	3437	405796	149663	28601	23922	3312	16762	953932
<i>Buffalo</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22	22
<i>Mutton</i>	6714	568	12290	12357	6457	1786	27	6819	800	9521	15128	43071	47343	162881
<i>Lamb</i>	11758	2450	868	24959	14876	1788	2461	11879	1639	1055	19104	17685	36185	146706
<i>Goat</i>	0	0	0	8550	2782	669	382	157	149	5160	89	0	1581	19519
<i>Pork</i>	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	1761	1331	40	26034	1	1568	30745
<i>Fancy Meat</i>	40	0	20627	1506	2154	14	1	26128	20001	2207	40929	7217	18061	138886
<i>Total</i>	26969	3025	46333	244086	124821	10429	6308	452540	173583	46585	125205	71287	121524	1452693

Prevention of Food Supply Contamination

Prevention of gastrointestinal Anthrax primarily relies on the avoidance of raw or partially cooked meat from any source. The carcasses of diseased animals carry the vegetative form of the bacterium and consumption may result in human infection.

Prevention and control of the disease in livestock is critical to reduce the incidence of Anthrax outbreaks. Sanitary farming and manufacturing practices coupled with a comprehensive vaccination programme maximize risk reduction strategies.[xxvii] Should infection of livestock occur, incineration of infected carcasses in burial pits is mandatory. This facilitates heat sterilization of the underlying soil. Site cleanup should involve the use of chemical agents such as peroxide and chlorine dioxide.

INFORMATION: RESPONSIBILITY & VIGILANCE

Community Information

The dissemination and control of information should be handled in a careful and orderly manner. Once an outbreak is confirmed by a District Veterinary Officer and notified to the Chief Veterinary Officer according to the AUSVET Emergency Plan, stakeholders and affected health bodies such as hospitals, local medical officers and diagnostic laboratories should be informed and regularly updated. Information to the general public should follow.

Managing Outbreak Severity

Environmental tests should be conducted in the affected and surrounding areas and appropriate measures taken for decontamination. Infected animals should be isolated and treated, and carcasses decomposed according to protocol. All contaminated areas are to be cleaned. Animal products should be tested for spores and export suspended if required.

Industry Involvement

The Australian CVO and industry should cooperatively establish a strategic plan for management of the outbreak. All trading partners should be informed of the outbreak by a nominated industry spokesperson. No further business can be done until health authorities have confirmed the complete closure of the outbreak.

Public Notification

Public enquiries should be directed to a special helpline coordinated with appropriate bodies: hospitals, emergency services, and detection squad. Informing people via news telecasts is quick and efficient. Support updates on radio and in newspapers should target the local community and provide hotline details. A campaign focused on preventive measures and information is crucial. Information outlets should be placed at a few locations for direct public enquiries.

Key Action Plan Objectives for Management of Anthrax Outbreak

1. **Veterinary confirmation of Anthrax in the field.**
2. **Notification to Department of Primary Industry.**
3. **Notification to Health Bodies: Hospitals, Laboratories, LMO, EM Services.**

4. Isolation of all livestock.
5. Notification of disease outbreak to neighboring farms, abattoirs, butchers, relevant industry and town residents.
6. Notification to local public of Anthrax outbreak – symptoms, treatment and vaccines.
7. Industry Statement to trading partners
8. Symptomatic livestock given antibiotics (BHC, 2007).
9. Vaccination of all animals at the location. (BHC, 2007)
10. Notification to surrounding farms to vaccinate.
11. Screening of farms and abattoirs for disease spread.
12. Burning and burying of carcasses to eliminate further contamination (BHC, 2007).

STATISTICS IN BRIEF

As evidenced by the table below, Australian states and territories have a low prevalence of *Bacillus anthracis*. They are well prepared to curtail and control outbreaks and thus the incidence of disease is low. Over the previous ten years there has been only one outbreak. Community training and preparedness should be regularly reviewed to ensure optimal response and management and to avoid complacency.

Table 3: Number of notifications of Anthrax, received from State and Territory health authorities in the period of 1991 to 2006

	ACT	NSW	NT	Qld	SA	Tas	Vic	WA	Aust
2001	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2002	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2003	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2004	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2005	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
2006	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1

Source: Communicable Diseases Authority, May 2007.

DISCUSSION

Preventing Anthrax in animals prevents Anthrax in humans. Recognizing this is the first step to minimizing and preventing the incidence of disease in the human population. In Australian communities at risk, such as the Hunter Valley community considered in this report, a well-prepared multi-agency response plan provides immeasurable advantage as does a well educated general public.

Most developing countries will have less developed meat or meat product export sectors than Australia, as this industry is high cost in infrastructure, land and trade requirements. Therefore the

economic impact of contamination of the meat supply may be barely felt on a macroeconomic level. However association of Anthrax with animal or hide products in any developing country will have significant potential to impede economic growth in cash markets, tourist markets and reliability of the domestic consumption markets. This has the potential to make considerable impact in the lives of those who need employment opportunities the most, the vulnerable unskilled or low skilled worker.

During an Anthrax outbreak, there is not time to waste. Precise management and execution of response is critical for containment and good health outcomes. The cornerstones of comprehensive primary health care are required immediately in these situations. Experienced epidemiologists, medical and veterinary clinical staff at the PHC and tertiary level, clinical specialists such as pathologists, nursing staff, public relations officers and exposure management teams all need to work together and provide urgent health care and community education to ensure maximum compliance with protocols and to enable containment to proceed with minimum diversion. Safety, prevention and vigilance must be a strong and clear message. Responsible surveillance, prevention and control of Anthrax outbreaks relies on rapid and coordinated multi-agency response at the emergent level. Adequate resourcing is required to expedite efficient and effective management of a potentially life threatening situation.

CONCLUSION

We are fortunate in Australia to have the resources and medical and political expediency to apply 'the gold standard' in communicable disease management. Even with these strengths our economic stability as a supplier of meat products domestically and to the world can and has been threatened. Surveillance is an expensive but necessary evil in the protection of economies and consumers and developing countries desperately need to protect their economic opportunities for the poor. Given the heavy demand on resources that public health and comprehensive primary health care management of Anthrax requires, outbreaks in developing countries are understandably less preventable, more frequent and more severe. However, it is precisely this deleterious paucity of multi-agency, comprehensive PHC, that is well-financed, self-sustaining, broad based, educative and supportive that fails to safeguard communities and results in costly accidents and loss of life.

CAUSATIVE ORGANISM	SYMPTOMS				TREATMENT	
	Syndrome	Incubation	Early	Late	First-line	Prognosis
Anthrax (<i>Bacillus anthracis</i>; gram positive, sporulating)	Pulmonary (Inhalational)	1-7 days	Fever, chills, nausea, vomiting, headache, cough, dyspnoea, chest pain, abdominal pain.	High fever, diaphoresis, cyanosis, hypotension, lymphadenopathy, shock, death (within 3 days of late symptom onset).	Ciprofloxacin, 400 mg IV q 12 h or Doxycycline, 200 mg IV, then 100 mg IV q 12 h. Without use of vaccine, treat for 60 days; with use of vaccine, treat for 30 days. As patient improves begin oral therapy.	95% Mortality
	Gastrointestinal (Upper)	1-7 days	Oral or oesophageal ulcer.	Regional lymphadenopathy, sepsis.	As above	50% Mortality
	Gastrointestinal (Lower)	1-7 days	Nausea & vomiting, diarrhea (bloody).	Acute abdomen, sepsis.	As above	50% Mortality
	Cutaneous	2 days	Pruritic papule → ulcer → vesicle → painless eschar.	Regional lymphadenopathy, occasional sepsis (1-2 weeks post onset)	As above	20% Mortality without treatment, 1% Mortality with treatment.

Table 1. Clinical Findings, Treatment and Prognosis for Anthrax Infection. [xxviii]

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Books & Periodicals:

- Albrink WS, Brooks SM, Biron RE, Kopel M. Human inhalation anthrax. *Am J Pathol* 1960;36:457-71.
- Jernigan JA, Stephens DS, Ashford DA, Omenaca C, Topiel MS, Galbraith M, et al. Bioterrorism-related inhalational anthrax: the first 10 cases reported in the United States. *Emerg Infect Dis* 2001;7:933-44.
- Abramova FA, Grinberg LM, Yampolskaya OV, Walker DH., **Pathology of inhalational anthrax in 42 cases from the Sverdlovsk outbreak of 1979.** Department of Pathology, Hospital 40, Ekaterinburg, Russia., *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* 1993 Mar 15;90(6):2291-4.
- Alizad A, Ayoub EM, Makki N. Intestinal anthrax in a two-year-old child. *Pediatr Infect Dis J* 1995;14:394-5.
- Bacteriology. Topley and Wilson's Principles of Bacteriology, Virology and Immunity. Vol. 2. Edward Arnold, Sevenoaks, England, 1990
- Baht P, Mohan DN, Srinivasa H. Intestinal anthrax with bacteriological investigations. *J Infect Dis* 1985;152:1357-8.
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Human ingestion of *Bacillus anthracis*-contaminated meat-Minnesota, August 2000. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 2000;49:813-6.
- Claus D, Berkeley RCW. Genus *Bacillus* Cohn 1872, 174AL. p. 1105. In Sneath PHA, Mair NS, Sharpe ME, Holt JG (eds): *Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology*. Vol. 2. Williams & Wilkins, Baltimore, 1986
- Davies JCA. A major epidemic of anthrax in Zimbabwe. *Cent Afr J Med* 1982;28:291-8.
- Sirisanthana T, Navachareon N, Tharavichitkul P, Sirisanthana V, Brown AE. Outbreak of oral-pharyngeal anthrax: an unusual manifestation of human infection with *Bacillus anthracis*. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 1984;33:144-50.
- Doganay M, Almac A, Hanagasi R. Primary throat anthrax. A report of six cases. *Scand J Infect Dis* 1986;18:415-9.
- Dixon TC, et al.: Anthrax. *N Engl J Med* 341:815, 1999.
- Dutz W, Saidi F, Kohout E. Gastric anthrax with massive ascites. *Gut* 1970;11:352-4.
- Heyworth B, Ropp ME, Voos UG, Meinel HI, Darlow HM. Anthrax in the Gambia: an epidemiological study. *Br Med J* 1975;4:79-82.
- Jena GP. Intestinal anthrax in man: a case report. *Cent Afr J Med* 1980;26:253-4.
- Kasper, D.L, et al (ed), *Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine*, pp 1280-1282, McGraw Hill 2005.
- Kasper D.L, et al. (ed) *Harrison's Manual of Medicine*, McGraw Hill pp118-119, 2005.
- Kohout E, Sehat A, Ashraf AM. Anthrax: a continuous problem in Southwest Iran. *Am J Med Sci* 1964;3:565-75.
- Kramer J.M, Gilbert RJ. *Bacillus cereus* and other *Bacillus* species. p.21. In Doyle MP (ed): *Foodborne Bacterial Pathogens*. Marcel Dekker, New York, 1989
- Kunanusont C, Limpakarnjanarat K, Foy JM. Outbreak of anthrax in Thailand. *Ann Trop Med Parasitol* 1990;84:507-12.
- Leppla S.H. The Anthrax toxin complex. p. 277. In Alouf JE, Freer JH (eds): *Sourcebook of Bacterial Proteins*. Academic Press, New York

Lincoln RE, Hodges DR, Klein F, et al. Role of the lymphatics in the pathogenesis of anthrax. *J Infect Dis* 1965;115:481-94.

Martin, E.A. (ed), *Concise Medical Dictionary*, p 202 Oxford University Press, 1994.

Microbiology, 6th ed. American Society for Microbiology, Washington, DC

Nalin DR, Sultana B, Sahunja R, Islam AK, Rahim MA, Islam M, et al. Survival of a patient with intestinal anthrax. *Am J Med* 1977;62:130-2.

Navacharoen N, Sirisanthana T, Navacharoen W, Ruckphaopunt K. Oropharyngeal anthrax. *J Laryngol Otol* 1985;99:1293-5.

Ndyabahinduka DGK, Chu IH, Abdou AH, Gaifuba JK. An outbreak of human gastrointestinal anthrax. *Annali dell Istituto Superiore di Sanita* 1984;20:205-8.

Onerci M, Ergin NT. Oropharyngealer Milzbrand (Oropharyngeal anthrax). *Laryngorhinootologie* 1993;72:350-1.

Parry J.M, Turnbull PCB, Gibson JR: *A Colour Atlas of Bacillus Species*. Wolfe Medical Atlas no. 19. Wolfe Publishing, London 1983

Perl DP, Dooley JR. Anthrax. In: Binford CH, Connor DH, editors. *Pathology of tropical and extraordinary diseases*. Washington: Armed Forces Institute of Pathology; 1976. p. 118-23.

Phonboon K, Ratanasiri P, Peeraprakorn S, Choomkasien P, Chongcharoen P, Sritasoi S. Anthrax outbreak in Udon Thani. *Communicable Disease Journal* 1984;10:207-20.

Schlossberg, D. (ed.), *Infections of Leisure*, pp 200-201 & 375, ASM Press, 1999.

Sekhar PC, Jaya Singh RS, Sridhar MS, Jaya Bhaskar C, Sreehari Rao Y. Outbreak of human anthrax in Ramabhadrapuram village of Chittoor district in Andhra Pradesh. *Indian J Med Res [A]* 1990;91:448-52.

Sirisanthana T, Jesadaporn U. Survival of a patient with gastrointestinal anthrax. *Chiang Mai Medical Bulletin* 1985;24:1-5.

Sirisanthana T, Nelson KE, Ezzell JW, Abshire TG. Serologic studies of patients with cutaneous and oral-oropharyngeal anthrax from northern Thailand. *Am J Trop Med Hyg* 1988;39:575-81.

Skerman, V.B.D.; McGowan, Vicki; Sneath, P.H.A., (eds) *Approved Lists of Bacterial Names*. Washington (DC): American Society for Microbiology; 1989

Stone, C.K. & Humphries, R.L. *Current Emergency Diagnosis and Treatment*, pp 22-25, Lange, 2004.

Tantajumroon T, Panas-Ampol K. Intestinal anthrax: report of two cases. *J Med Assoc Thai* 1968;51:477-80.

Tantachumroon T. Pathologic studies of intestinal anthrax: report of 2 cases. *Chiang Mai Medical Bulletin* 1966;4:135-44.

Turnbull P.C.B: Anthrax. p. 364. In Smith G.R, Easmon C.R (eds): *Bacterial Diseases*.

Topley and Wilson's *Principles of Bacteriology, Virology and Immunity*. Vol 3. Edward Arnold. Sevenoaks, England, 1990

Turnbull PCB, Kramer JM: *Bacillus* . p. 349. In Murray P.R, et al. (eds): Manual of Clinical

Turnbull PCB, Kramer JM, Melling J: *Bacillus* . p. 187. In Parker MT, Duerden BI (eds): Systematic

Underwood J.C.E, *General and Systematic Pathology*, pp 381-3, 680, 756-8, 2004.

Viratchai C. Anthrax gastro-enteritis and meningitis. J Med Assoc Thai 1974;57:147-50.

Websites:

Centres for Disease Control and Prevention:

<http://www.bt.cdc.gov/agent/Anthrax>

Harrison's Manual of Internal Medicine, 16th ed, online:

<http://www.Harrisons16.com>

Access Medicine

Online_ <http://www.accessmedicine.com/content.aspx?alD=2530386&searchStr=Anthrax>

National Centre for Biotechnology Information

<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/bv.fcgi?rid=mmed.biblist.953>

Meat and Livestock Australia, 2006 "South East Asia/Chinas Update" Newsletter December 2006

Australian Government Health.vic.gov website

<http://www.health.gov.au/internet/main/publishing.nsf/Content/ohp-surv-isr-02-08.htm>

Australian Bureau of Statistics, "Australia's Beef Cattle Industry" Year Book Australia 2005

Panafrican News Agency Africa 2003, "Zimbabwe beef export earnings see drastic fall"

PANA Daily News Wire, 22 July 2003

BBC Monitoring Service: Africa, 2000 "Anthrax outbreak reported in Mashonaland West Province" ZBC Radio, Harare, 19 August 1997

Skelton, R 1997 'Anthrax Sparks Beef, Dairy Exports Freeze', The Sydney Morning Herald

American Journal of Public Health Website, Anthrax and the Wool Trade:

<http://www.ajph.org/cgi/content/full/92/5/754>

Nation Multimedia Group Public Co, 2000 "Anthrax Infects Another Victim" The Nation (Thailand)

Meat and Livestock Australia, <http://www.mla.com.au>

Millar, H & Attwood 2006, Anthrax in Animals, The State of Victoria

<http://www.dpi.vic.gov.au/dpi/nreninf.nsf/LinkView/0C337BDB64C357AFCA256BCF000BBD2A323F5CFE0267D9674A256DEA00273B5A>

Commonwealth of Australia 2003, Anthrax Fact sheet, Australian Government, Department of Health and Ageing, http://www.health.gov.au/internet/wcms/publishing.nsf/Content/health-publth-strateg-communic-factsheets-Anthrax_fact.htm

Country Chat 2007, 'Who needs to know about Anthrax?' Shepparton News, <http://www.sheppnews.com.au/blogs/Countrychat/comments.asp?id=291>>

Mayo Clinic Staff 2006, Anthrax, Mayo Foundation for Medical Education and Research, <http://www.mayoclinic.com/health/Anthrax/DS00422/DSECTION=8>

Infectious Disease, Bacillus anthraci, Historique.net, <http://microbes.historique.net/images/Anthrax2.gif>

Department of Health and Human Services 2006, Questions and Answers About Anthrax, Centre for Disease Control and Prevention <http://www.bt.cdc.gov/agent/anthrax/faq/>

Peter Warfe 2005, Human research ethics in the Australian Defence Force, ADF Health http://www.defence.gov.au/dpe/dhs/infocentre/publications/journals/NoIDs/adfhealth_apr05/ADFHealth_6_1_26-29.html

Emergency Health Services Department, Consultative Committee on Emergency Animal Disease (CCEAD), Commonwealth of Australia <http://www.affa.gov.au/content/output.cfm?ObjectID=0098057A-8A45-4CD1-911F238F127567BA>

Department of Health and Human Services 2005, Anthrax, Centre for Disease Control and Prevention http://www.cdc.gov/ncidod/dbmd/diseaseinfo/Anthrax_g.htm#preventinf>
Animal Health Australia, Disease Strategy Anthrax Version 3.2 2005, Pg.28 & 37, Commonwealth of Australia

Communicable disease Control, Public Health Branch, Rural & Regional Health & Aged Care Services Division 2007, Anthrax, Victorian State Government, Department of Human Services, Australia <http://www.health.vic.gov.au/ideas/bluebook/Anthrax>

Homeland Security National Terror Alert, Anthrax Treatment, The National Terror alert response Centre <http://www.nationalterroralert.com/Anthraxtreatment>

Health State, Anthrax http://www.health.state.ny.us/diseases/communicable/Anthrax/fact_sheet.htm

Mayoclinic, Anthrax: Screening and diagnosis <http://www.mayoclinic.com/health/Anthrax/DS00422/DSECTION=6>

Lungusa, Anthrax <http://www.lungusa.org/site/pp.asp?c=dvLUK9O0E&b=35111>

Medical Encyclopedia, Anthrax <http://www.nlm.nih.gov/medlineplus/print/ency/article/001325.htm>

Anthrax, UC Davis veterinary Medicine Extension http://www.vetmed.ucdavis.edu/vetext/INF-DA/INF-DA_Anthrax.html

Cattle diseases- Anthrax <http://cattletoday.info/Anthrax.htm>

AACC

http://www.aacc.org/AACC/events/expert_access/2002/rapid/qanda.htm

J Clin Microbiol, Detection of Bacillus anthracis DNA by LightCycler

<http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/articlerender.fcgi?artid=120654>

CDC Anthrax Q&A : Laboratory testing

<http://www.bt.cdc.gov/agent/Anthrax/faq/labtesting.asp>

Entrez PubMed

http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/entrez/query.fcgi?cmd=Retrieve&db=PubMed&dopt=Citation&list_uids=16467327

NNii. Vaccine Information

http://www.immunizationinfo.org/vaccineInfo/vaccine_detail.cfv?id=25

Food Standards Australia and New Zealand website:

<http://www.foodstandards.gov.au/newsroom/factsheets/factsheets2002/Anthraxandfoodsafety1316.cfm>

http://www.hpa.org.uk/infections/topics_az/deliberate_release/Anthrax/OrganismDetails.asp?Source=Professional&Agent=Anthrax&Document=OrganismDetails

http://www.vetmed.ucdavis.edu/vetext/INF-DA/INF-DA_Anthrax.html

<http://www.ph.ucla.edu/epi/Bioter/Anthraxsdoggeddetective.html>

BBC News, 2006. 'Simple' way to test for Anthrax.

<http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/health/5262440.stm>

Capaldi, L, 2000. Antrax- Human vaccines.

http://www.brown.edu/Courses/Bio_160/Projects2000/Anthrax/vaccines/human.html

CDC- Centers for disease control and prevention, 2006. Anthrax Q & A: Laboratory Testing.

<http://www.bt.cdc.gov/agent/Anthrax/faq/labtesting.asp>

Department of Health. 2004. Anthrax(malignant edema, woolsorters' disease).

http://www.health.state.ny.us/diseases/communicable/Anthrax/fact_sheet.htm,

Navarre, CB, Sanson, D. 2007. Comprehensive, Coordinated Animal Identification A Must for Food Safety, National Security.

<http://www.lsuagcenter.com/en/communications/publications/agmag/Archive/2007/Winter/Comprehensive+Coordinated+Animal+Identification+A+Must+for+Food+Safety+National+Security.htm>

FSANZ, 2006, Australia New Zealand Food Standards code, Australian Food News,

<http://www.ausfoodnews.com.au/db/node/3153>

Paskin. R, year not listed, Manual on Livestock Disease Surveillance and Information Systems, EMPRES/Infectious Diseases Group

<http://www.fao.org/ag/AGA/AGAH/EMPRES/Info/other/surveill.htm#Table>

Hughes, J.M and Gerberding, J.L, 2002, Anthrax Bioterrorism: Lessons Learned and Future Directions, CDC
<http://www.cdc.gov/ncidod/EID/vol8no10/02-0466.htm>

LookSmart, 2002, Inactivate Anthrax spores with non-toxic heat: Innovative technology tested at environmental company- Precision Environmental Inc - Brief Article, LookSmart,
http://findarticles.com/p/articles/mi_m0ISW/is_2002_Feb-March/ai_82881759

Australian Broadcasting Corporation (ABC), 2003, Anthrax vaccine safe: Hill (TV program transcript), ABC.
<http://www.abc.net.au/lateline/stories/s783068.htm>

Commonwealth of Australia, 2003. Anthrax Fact Sheet, Australian Government Department of Health and Ageing. http://www.health.gov.au/internet/wcms/publishing.nsf/Content/health-pubhlth-strateg-communic-factsheets-Anthrax_fact.htm

CDC. 2005. Division of bacterial and mycotic diseases: Anthrax, Centers for Disease Control and Protection
http://www.cdc.gov/ncidod/dbmd/diseaseinfo/Anthrax_g.htm#Where%20is%20Anthrax%20usually%20found

Consumer Freedom. 2007. Mad Cow Disease, Centre for Consumer Freedom <http://www.consumerfreedom.com/issuepage.cfm/topic/5>

FAO. 2001. Spotlight: Anthrax in Animals, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
<http://www.fao.org/AG/magazine/0112sp.htm>

Todar's Textbook of Bacteriology. 2005. Bacillus anthracis and Anthrax, Kenneth Todar University of Wisconsin-Madison Department of Bacteriology. <http://textbookofbacteriology.net/Anthrax.html>

Centre for Disease Control, 2005. Anthrax.
http://www.cdc.gov/ncidod/dbmd/diseaseinfo/Anthrax_g.htm#preventinf

Massachusetts Medical Society, 1999. Anthrax.
<http://content.nejm.org/cgi/reprint/341/11/815.pdf?ck=nck>

Regional Animal Disease Surveillance and Control Network, 1997. News@Radiscon.
<http://www.fao.org/ag/AGA/AGAH/ID/Radiscon/News3-e.htm>

World Health Organization, 2007. Anthrax
<http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs264/en>

CNN
<http://i.cnn.net/cnn/2002/US/03/26/Anthrax.investigation/story.microscope.jpg>

Access Emergency Medicine
http://www.accessemergencymedicine.com/public/about_aem.aspx,

search.com
www.search.com

The Emergency Medicine Mag

Quadrant HealthCom Inc, <http://www.emedmag.com/html/pre/ter/BT1201.asp>

United States Army Medical Research Institute of Infectious Diseases: *USAMRIID's Medical Management of Biological Casualties Handbook*, 4th edition, February 2001. <http://www.usamriid.army.mil/education/bluebook.html>

Swartz MN: Recognition and management of Anthrax: An update. *N Engl J Med* November 6, 2001. www.nejm.org

Post Graduate Subject Reading Lists:

International Health and Primary Health Care (2010)
Centre for International Health - Curtin University

Economics of Health Financing (2011)
Centre for International Health - Curtin University

Photographs:

Fig 1 <http://i.cnn.net/cnn/2002/US/03/26/Anthrax.investigation/story.microscope.jpg>

Fig 2 www.search.com/reference/Anthrax

Fig 3 www.cdc.gov/ncidod/EID/vol9no5/02-0537-G2.htm

[i] Anthrax of the Gastro-intestinal tract, Medscape.

[ii] Ibid

[iii] CDC, Emerging infectious diseases

[iv] Ibid

[v] MEDSCAPE website, article 437391

[vi] Ibid

[vii] WHO/Europe, 2006

[viii] Pathology of inhalational anthrax in 42 cases from the Sverdlovsk outbreak of 1979.

[ix] International Surveillance Reports, 2008, Dept of Health and Ageing. www.health.gov.au

[x] Outbreak of human anthrax in Ramabhadrapuram village of Chittoor district in Andhra Pradesh

[xi] Anthrax of the Gastro-intestinal tract

[xii] Kasper, 2005

[xiii] Stone & Humphries, 2004

[xiv] Ibid

[xv] Schlossberg, 1999.

[xvi] Stone & Humphries, 2004

[xvii] Ibid

[xviii] Kasper, 2005

[xix] Stone & Humphries, 2004

[xx] National Agricultural Bio-security Center, Anthrax fact sheet

[xxi] Cattle diseases - Anthrax, 2007.

[xxii] National Agricultural Biosecurity Center, Anthrax fact sheet.

[xxiii] Health State, Anthrax, 2004

[xxiv] Lungusa, Anthrax, 2007

[xxv] Dept Health and Ageing, 2003.

[xxvi] Orbinger, 2007.

[xxvii] APHIS USDA website, Anthrax – General information and vaccination.

[xxviii] Stone, C.K. & Humphries, 2004